

Comparison of Emotional Facial Expressions and Responses to Speech and Emotional Words, Also Called POFA

Assoc. Prof. Eren Ersoy

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Abstract

Affective for emotionally charged phrases are photographs of facial expressions depicting a range of emotions. These photographs are also known as Facial Effect Pictures (POFA). standards established by the International Affective Dictionary of the English Language (ANEW) and emotional voices The individual components of this work include all of the research that has been conducted on the Digitized Sound System (IDAS). Because of the capabilities of these technologies, researchers are able to determine how the hemodynamic responses of the brain are impacted, and thus, this process is carried out (indirect measurement). Electroencephalography, more often referred to by its acronym EEG, is a technique that directly investigates the electrical dynamics of the brain in relation to reactions to mental and emotional activities. An electroencephalogram is another term that may be used to refer to this test. The mapping of brain activity is a common use of the functional neuroimaging technique known as functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI). The primary factor contributing to this finding is the excellent spatial resolution that the imaging technology in issue has (a few millimeters). This was done with the intention of determining whether or not the presence of emotionally charged information has an influence on the improvement of memory. The findings led the researchers to the conclusion that the successful retrieval of emotionally charged photographs requires more activation of the amygdala, as well as the entorhinal cortex and the hippocampus, than is required for recalling images that do not contain any emotional charge whatsoever. When the individuals were asked to recall anything, the levels of activity in the amygdala and hippocampus were much greater than when they were asked to identify familiar faces. On the other hand, when individuals were asked to recollect earlier experiences or identify known faces, there was no change at all in the activity levels in the entorhinal cortex. In addition, one research examines the influence of motivation on episodic memory by varying the level of difficulty of the task. The motivation in this study was either a low or high monetary reward.

Keywords: POFA, Emotional Facial Expressions, Responses to Speech, Emotional Words, POFA and Its Effects in Psychology

1. Introduction

The purpose of this essay is to put theories to the test. Data from functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) of the nigra/VTA demonstrates higher activity in the medial temporal lobe (MTL) and dorsolateral prefrontal cortex (dmPFC) when retrieval is accomplished with a high level of effort compared than with a low level of difficulty (DLPFC). When both the precision of the retrieval and the subject's motivation are strong,

1. *SN/VTA-MTL and*
2. *SN/VTA- dmPFC*

Connections that are functionally connected to rewards between

Using a technique known as functional magnetic resonance imaging, or fMRI, it is feasible to acquire an indirect measurement of the hemodynamic response. The monitoring of variations in the local ratios of oxy-hemoglobin to deoxy-hemoglobin, commonly known as blood oxygenation level-dependent or BOLD signal, is how this is achieved (Cabeza and Nyberg , 2000). Dolcos et al. (2005) examined the effects of emotional content on memory improvement during retrieval by using event-related fMRI to measure retrieval-related effectiveness after a one-year retention period. This was done in order to determine whether or not emotional content enhances memory. Their findings were just published in the peer-reviewed journal NeuroImage. According to the findings that were discovered by Shigemune et al. (2017), the network that is comprised of the SN/VTA (reward-related), the dmPFC (motivation-related), and the MTL (memory-related) network modulates reward- and motivation-related memory in addition to the DLPFC (cognitive controls) network. When things were challenging, it was all about personal growth. When considered as a whole, these findings point to the amygdala and the medial temporal lobe (MTL) as having significant contributions to make to the process of remembering emotional and motivated memories. According to the results of yet another fMRI investigation, the presence of

neural activity in the bilateral amygdala, hippocampus, and parahippocampus was related with a higher success rate for emotional recollection (emotional hits > misses);

- *On the other hand, a higher success rate for neutral retrieval was associated with greater activity in the right posterior parahippocampus regions (Shafer and Dolcos , 2014).*

As a result of this, functional magnetic resonance imaging, often known as fMRI, has produced compelling evidence of connections between cognitive and emotional brain networks during the processing of information, especially in reaction to emotionally charged content. These interactions seem to have an influence not just on the consolidation of memories but also on the processes of encoding and retrieval, which are the fundamental building blocks of efficient long-term memory formation and memory recall. Activation of the amygdala, in other words, seems to exert control over both the hippocampus and the visual cortex while the process of visual perception is taking place. The "bottom-up" approach to higher cognitive functions, which is centered on awareness, eventually leads to an improvement in the selection and organizing of important information as a consequence of the process. The functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) technique has many drawbacks, the most significant of which are its low temporal resolution, its high initial setup costs, and the difficulty of keeping a person still in an electromagnetically separated room while the procedure is being performed.

The following are other problems:

Despite its widespread use, functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) has a number of limitations; the most important of which are its poor temporal resolution, expensive initial setup costs, and the difficulty of keeping a person motionless in an electromagnetically shielded environment, the environment (immobility).

Also, functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) is slightly slower metabolically because the BOLD signal exhibits an initial decline, the subsequent signal's increase is delayed by 2-3 seconds, and it takes approximately 6-12 seconds to reach this value. This delay is due to the fact that the signal is trying to reflect the neural responses that are elicited by a stimulus. is a peak value. This

is due to the fact that the BOLD signal demonstrates an initial dip followed by a delay of two to three seconds in the rise of the next signal, the BOLD signal demonstrates an initial dip followed by a delay of two to three seconds in the rise of the next signal, and also the BOLD signal demonstrates an initial dip (Logothetis et al., 2001). This suggests that functional magnetic resonance imaging, or fMRI, does not provide an efficient method for visualizing subcortical regions like the mesencephalon because it has a poor temporal resolution (a few seconds), in contrast to electrophysiological techniques (which provide a resolution of a few milliseconds) (brainstem, metabolic activity is greater than that of PET). because of how slowly it moves). People often imply positron emission tomography (also known as PET) when they say they are talking about PET (positron emission tomography). One other technique that may be used for functional neuroimaging is called positron emission tomography. This approach provides a map of the activity of the brain as well as a map of the physiology of the central nervous system by the measurement of glucose metabolism or regional cerebral blood flow. The positron emission tomography was developed during the decade of the 1970s (rCBF). In positron emission tomography (PET), in addition to the usage of other related substances, positron emitting radionuclides such as ^{18}F -fluorodeoxyglucose (FDG) and the positron emitting oxygen isotope tagged with water (^{15}O]HO) are used. The use of this technology makes it possible to pinpoint specific regions of the brain that are involved in the experience of positive emotions, negative emotions, and neutral emotions (Lane et al., 1997).

The brain is directly involved in the processing of both positive and negative emotions. seems to be linked to increased regional cerebral blood flow (rCBF) in some areas of the medial prefrontal cortex (mPFC), thalamus, and hypothalamus. The midbrain also appears to be affected. The bilateral occipital cortex (OTC), the cerebellum, the left parahippocampal gyrus, the hippocampus, and the amygdala are some of the brain areas that are more firmly related with the sense of unpleasant emotions. The use of PET scanning provided evidence for the existence of a connection between the processing of emotional information and the consolidation of visual memories. In addition to that, the caudate nucleus is reliant on the finding of this relationship. This association is created as a consequence of interactions between the perceptual and memory processing systems, especially in response to lingual inputs. In particular, this interaction is responsible for establishing the connection between the two concepts. an increase in the level of activity inside the gyrus (Taylor et al., 1998).

The results also demonstrated that the existence of a highly negative emotional value made it easier to comprehend early sensory data. This was shown to be the case. Data support this understanding of the situation. The fact that the processing of early sensory data was streamlined is evidence that this is the case. This may be shown by making it more straightforward. Additionally abandoned amygdaloid at the coding stage While there are differences in brain activity in the brain complex (AC), in the recognition memory process, in the right prefrontal cortex (PFC), and medial responses were detected in the prefrontal cortex, while there are differences in brain activity in the brain complex (AC) (mPFC). Tataranni et al. (1999) identified regions of the central nervous system (CNS) that are associated with appetitive states including hunger and satiety. This is analogous to how this is carried out (Tataranni et al., 1999).

2. Hypothalamus Connections

Participating structures include the hypothalamus, the insular cortex, limbic and paralimbic regions (including the anterior cingulate cortex, the parahippocampal and hippocampal formation, the anterior temporal and posterior orbitofrontal cortex), the thalamus, the caudate, the precuneus, the putamen, and the cerebellum. increased rCBF levels as a direct consequence of hunger bilateral ventromedial prefrontal cortex, dorsolateral prefrontal cortex, and inferior parietal A higher rate of rCBF absorption in the lobule was shown to be linked with saturation. These results imply that;

- *emotion and motivation are related to hunger, which refers to uncomfortable emotions (discomfort, pain, and anxiety) for the regulation of food intake;*
- *prefrontal cortex, which is associated with inhibition of inappropriate behavioral response , is involved in satiety, which signals excessive food consumption to end a meal ; And*
- *The hypothalamus, which is associated with the regulation of various physiological processes, is involved in control.). In addition, neuroanatomical mapping of emotions (Davidson and Irwin, 1999), emotional processing (Choudhary et al., 2015), and cognitive processes have been completed with the help of PET scanning (Cabeza and Nyberg , 2000).*

PET scanning is invasive, despite the fact that it offers a high level of spatial resolution for the examination of brain and body functions. Despite the fact that this offers no such resolution. However, the price is unreasonable, it does not give as great of a degree of temporal precision as EEG does, and fMRI does not need the patient to go through any intrusive procedures in order to get the results they need. In addition, in comparison to fMRI, PET has a tendency to detect increased activity in older parts of the brain, namely the mesencephalon and the brainstem. It is because of this that its use in the clinical diagnosis of neurological disease processes (such as epilepsy and Alzheimer's disease), cardiovascular disorders, and cancers is often restricted. Electroencephalography allows for a high temporal resolution to be achieved in a matter of milliseconds by attaching electrodes to the scalp in order to capture the electrical activity of the brain. Electroencephalography is what is meant to be represented by the acronym EEG (EEG). When using this method, it is also feasible to deliver treatments that do not need any kind of invasive procedure, do not call for a significant amount of money, and may be carried out in a setting that is easily portable. In addition, a number of studies have shown that the EEG is useful in mapping the mental and emotional processes that are controlled by the central nervous system (CNS). The completion of these investigations was made possible by the contributions of a large number of researchers. Using this method, one may perform a wide variety of feature extraction and analysis methods, some examples of which are EEG coherence analysis, phase delay analysis, cross power analysis, and power spectrum analysis. A comparison of the strengths of two or more signals is what's known as a cross-power analysis, and it's one kind of analysis. The authors of one research (Paré et al., 2002) explored changes in EEG oscillations that occur in the amygdala during the consolidation of emotionally charged memories displaying theta (4-8 Hz) activity. They found that these changes occurred in the amygdala. This was carried out as part of a research that was looking at the amygdala during the process of consolidating memories that were emotionally charged. The findings of this research indicate that engaging in theta activity helps to solidify memories, enhances one's ability to retain emotionally charged information, and enhances one's ability to remember memories. This finding was subsequently supported by the discovery of increased theta activity in the right frontal (Friese et al., 2013) and right temporal (Sederberg et al., 2003) cortices, and as a result, was associated with successful encoding of new information. [Citation needed] This stimulation of the hippocampus was connected to the

reception of sensory information, motor activity, and memory. It is a representation of the active state of the brain that takes place during the processing of information connected with the hippocampus while its processing takes place. Learning and memory rely heavily on a phenomenon known as synaptic plasticity, which is sometimes referred to as synaptic change. This shift occurred as a consequence of a link that was established between the pyramidal cell dendrites, the Schaffer collateral, and the entorhinal cortex (the Schaffer collateral may be found in the CA3 area of the brain) (found in both CA3 and CA1). The interaction between the two causes the production of theta waves as a direct consequence of the interaction. As a consequence of this, there is now a higher level of confidence in the idea that the process of encoding new memories is connected to the phenomenon of theta wave release. During the processing of withdrawal and avoidance, research using electroencephalography has also indicated an alpha asymmetry in the prefrontal lobes of the brain.

An inverse association exists between the intensity of alpha waves in an EEG and the activity of the cortex, which indicates that a lower alpha power is connected with more activity. This can be seen by the fact that an increase in alpha power is related with a decrease in activity. One other way to phrase this would be to say that "a lower alpha power is connected with increased activity" (inhibition). A researcher by the name of Davidson (1988) was the one who came up with the concept for the frontal asymmetry measure and was the one who initially presented it. Either by using the website www.frontiersin.org or by computing a ratio of the variances in log-transform power levels between left frontal and right frontal alpha power, he was able to accomplish this goal. As the preferred electrodes, the homologous pairs F3-F4 and F7-F8 were chosen to function in this capacity. This is because of a factor known as cortical inhibition, which is being taken into account. Therefore, when the outcome is positive, activity is indicated in the left anterior cortex, which is associated with positive emotions and the desire for intimacy, whereas when the outcome is negative, activity is indicated in the right anterior cortex, which is associated with negative emotions and the desire for intimacy. away is shown if the value being examined is negative. Therefore, right frontal activity is the consequence of more right alpha power (right frontal activation) than left alpha power (left frontal activation), while left frontal activity is the result of more right alpha power (right frontal activation) than left alpha power (left frontal activation). More left alpha power is generated as a consequence of right frontal activity than right frontal activation. More right frontal activation leads to greater left alpha strength than right frontal

activity does, and the converse is also true: right frontal activity leads to more right frontal activation. According to the findings of a second research, higher levels of alpha activity in the left frontal area were related with a desire to approach, while higher levels of alpha activity in the right frontal region were connected with a desire to recede. It turns out that each of these relationships was followed by a decrease in the alpha power in the frontal areas to which they are related (Harmon -Jones et al., 2010). According to these results, the alpha asymmetry of the EEG may be utilized to differentiate between "approach," which is represented by a positive value, and "withdrawal," which is represented by a negative value.

3. Comparing Student's Brain Activity

On the other hand, it was found that pleasure, which is associated with the drive to approach but has a positive value, has more left frontal activity than anger, which is associated with the drive to approach but has a negative value. This was found to be the case when the two emotions were compared to each other. This was the situation for the simple reason that pleasure has a beneficial value. Researchers analyzed patterns of brain activity related with happy and sad states and came to this finding as a result of their investigation (Harmon -Jones and Gable , 2017). An asymmetry inhibition model of alpha activity can be used to regulate the processing of emotional distractions, as indicated by the findings of a study. This model incorporates two inhibitory executive control processes. This model can be used to achieve regulation of the processing of emotional distractions. The purpose of this model is to accomplish the regulation of the processing of emotional distractions, and it is intended to do so. You may get an explanation of these processes by looking at the following:

- *The left prefrontal cortex inhibits the processing of negative or withdrawal-related distractors ; And*
- *right prefrontal cortex inhibits processing of positive or approach-related distractors.*

The valence theory and the motivational direction hypothesis were both useful in disclosing these discrepancies, and they both contributed to the overall revelation of the contradictions (Grimshaw and Carmel , 2014). There is a link between a rise in alpha activity and a fall in activity in the

frontoparietal area, and this association exists. This is due to the fact that the fronto-parietal network and the alpha network have a significant link that goes in the opposite way. This decrease in activity in the frontal and parietal lobes is a reflection of the executive control mechanism that minimizes interference from minor emotional distractors by preventing the frontal and parietal lobes from being overactive. In other words, the executive control mechanism keeps the frontal and parietal lobes from becoming overactive. When 148 right-handed female individuals were asked to acquire and remember knowledge, Headley and Paré (2013) found that there was an increase in gamma release in the neocortex and right amygdala of those participants. This was created by the emotionally powerful pictures, which induced a rise in gamma oscillation, which ultimately led to this conclusion. The emotional intensity of the sights was what sparked this. It was required of the participants that they take part in tasks that included learning and recalling information. When subjects were given pictures of negative value, Müller et al. (1999) showed that gamma potentials rose in the left anterior and temporal portions of the brain. This discovery was made after a more in-depth investigation was conducted. In contrast, reactions to pictures that had a positive value resulted in a rise in gamma band activity in the right frontal lobes of 11 individuals who were right-handed. When people participated in activities that made them feel emotionally good, another research discovered a large increase in theta-alpha coherence between the prefrontal and posterior parietal regions of the EEG (Aftanas and Golocheikine, 2001). They came to the conclusion that the shift was linked to an increase in attention, which was linked, in turn, to improved performance in memory and emotional processing. They came to the realization as a result of this that the shift was associated with higher attention. As a consequence of this, we have a number of EEG studies that compare the activity of the left and right hemispheres when processing positive (pleasant) and negative (unpleasant) stimuli. The findings of these studies suggest that different levels of electrical activation occur in different regions of the brain. This is due to the fact that the left and right hemispheres of the brain perform distinct functions while processing positive (pleasant) and negative (unpleasant) information. In these investigations, human volunteers and rats served as the subjects of the research. When compared to functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) and positron emission tomography (PET), the spatial resolution of electroencephalography (EEG) ranges from around 5 to 9 cm, which is regarded to be rather poor (Babiloni et al., 2001).

4. Different Effects on Volume Delivery

As a consequence of the effects of the cortex, dura mater, skull, and scalp on volume conduction, the scalp potentials are diminished. As a direct consequence of this, the potential of the scalp is diminished. There are several limitations to the electroencephalogram's capacity to evaluate activity that takes place at levels below the brain. As a result, it is only feasible to discover patterns of electromagnetic fields that are connected to the flow of current in the brain with a certain degree of precision. Subsequent research has demonstrated that the spatial resolution of EEG recordings can be enhanced by combining high-resolution EEG (high-density electrode arrays to increase spatial sampling) with superficial Laplace estimation and cortical imaging. However, a discussion of the specifics of this field is outside the purview of this review. See Nunez et al., 1994 for theoretical and experimental studies, or by merging various imaging modalities that offer complimentary information (such EEG-fMRI and EE), for example (Dale and Halgren , 2001).

5. Near Infrared (fNIRS) Imaging

Imaging with functional near-infrared spectroscopy, also known as near-infrared spectroscopy (fNIRS), is a relatively new technology that was developed through the use of functional near-infrared spectroscopy. This method of imaging is not only non-invasive and portable, but it also has a significantly lower cost than other imaging techniques. It allows for the mapping of hemodynamic responses that are caused by the stimulation of the brain. This technique positions light emitters and detectors, known as optodes, on the scalp in order to monitor changes in the concentration of oxygenated hemoglobin (oxy-Hb) and deoxygenated hemoglobin (deoxy-Hb) in the brain. The optodes monitor the concentration of oxygenated hemoglobin (oxy-Hb) in the brain. The quantity of oxygenated hemoglobin is weighed against the quantity of deoxygenated hemoglobin to arrive at this conclusion. In a nutshell, the method entails contrasting the quantity of oxygenated hemoglobin with the quantity of deoxygenated hemoglobin (Villringer et al ., 1993). It is only possible to visualize activity in cortical regions, not activity in subcortical regions, and the only conclusion that can be drawn from the findings is that increased brain activity is associated with increased consumption of glucose and oxygen. This limitation severely limits the utility of the study. Due to the nature of this restriction, it is not feasible to arrive at any additional conclusions based on the study. Changes in the local cerebral blood oxygenation may be evaluated

via optical penetration if there are increases in cerebral blood flow and oxygen delivery that are larger than the baseline level of oxygen consumption. These gains are the direct consequence of keeping the same level of oxygen intake as before. Physical exercise (Perrey, 2008), cognitive load (Durantin et al., 2014), mental difficulties (Ehlis et al., 2014), emotional processing (Bendell et al., 2016), and aging are all factors that are included in this category. In addition to that, it has been linked to the aging process. There is a correlation between the total quantity of labor and the number of studies that have used this particular research methodology (Villringer et al., 1993). It has been proven that maintaining social connections, engaging in mentally taxing activities (Durantin et al., 2014), and engaging in physical activity (Perrey, 2008) are all helpful for one's mental and physical health (Hock et al., 1995). In a study, functional magnetic resonance imaging spectroscopy, also known as fNIRS, was used so that researchers could investigate the relationship between shifts in emotional state and self-reported levels of happiness (Oonishi et al., 2014). The findings of the research indicated that the quantity of subjective pleasure experienced by the participants had an impact on the left-right prefrontal cortex (PFC) activation pattern that takes place when they participate in activities connected to emotion. An increase in oxy-Hb was found to occur in the left prefrontal cortex (PFC) while seeing pleasant photographs, whereas an increase in oxy-Hb was found to occur in the right prefrontal cortex (PFC) when watching unpleasant photos, as shown by the findings of the study. It was noted that there was an increase in the levels of Oxy-Hb, and this rise was detected in both the right and the left VLPFC. This rise has been demonstrated to be connected with a feeling of experiencing unpleasant emotional stimuli. [Case in point:] [Case in point:] [Case In addition, the left ventrolateral in the prefrontal cortex and the right ventrolateral in the prefrontal cortex (BA45/47) A technique of stimulation analogous to this occurrence was applied to a number of regions in the prefrontal cortex, including BA10, 45, 46, and 47. According to the findings of yet another fNIRS research (BA46/10), being exposed to pleasant emotional stimuli was related with lower levels of oxy-Hb in the left DLPFC. This relationship emerged after exposing participants to emotionally charged images over a period of six seconds. When photographs that evoked strong emotions were shown, this was the result. This took place as a direct consequence of the display of content that was visually appealing (Hoshi et al., 2011). The findings of this research indicate that the left hemisphere is responsible for processing information that is associated with approach, while the right hemisphere is responsible for processing information that is associated with retreat. As a direct consequence of this, the

processing of information pertaining to approaches is shifted over to the left hemisphere of the brain (Davidson, 1992; Davidson & Irwin, 1999).

6. Asymmetry of the Frontal Hemisphere

These results addressing the asymmetry of the frontal hemisphere may seem to be contradictory; nevertheless, it is likely that these findings are the result of a comparison of state-related changes rather than baseline levels of asymmetry. This is one potential explanation for these findings. As a consequence of this, there are many distinct aspects that need to be kept in mind, including the following:

hemispheric asymmetry. Davidson, 2004).

In another study that made use of fNIRS, researchers looked at the potential of a connection between the proper function of a person's prefrontal cortex and their capacity to exercise effective cognitive control over their emotions (Ozawa et al., 2014). After looking at emotionally charged IAPS photographs for 5.2 seconds, the subject began the n-back task. After that, the individual was given neutral photos. On the other hand, some research have shown that the reactions of the amygdala to images are located on the right side of the brain. This adds support to the theory that the amygdala evokes different reactions depending on the type of the stimulus that is presented to it (Pegna et al., 2005). However, a large number of studies point to the likelihood of differences in lateralization depending on gender (Hamann, 2005), individual personality (Hamann & Lively, 2004), mood (Rusting, 1998), age (Allard & Kensinger, 2014), and sleep (Walker). shows, 2009), the subject's stimulus awareness (Morris et al., 1998), stress (Payne et al., 2007), and a variety of other factors. These observations support the following theory, which can be found here:

These findings are in agreement with the hypothesis that Hamann's investigation is one of them (2005). As a consequence of this, it is of the utmost significance that the aforementioned problems be taken into consideration in the subsequent investigation. In this research, healthy native German speakers were given emotional phrases and facial expressions to stimulate them, and event-related potentials (ERPs), which are more popularly known as ERPs, were utilized to assess the modality

effects that resulted from this combination of stimuli. Participants in this study all had German as their first language, and the research was carried out in Germany. All of the individuals in this research had healthy levels of physical fitness (Schacht and Sommer , 2009a). In this particular experiment, in addition to smiling faces, angry faces, neutral faces, and significantly distorted versions of neutral faces, German verbs or nicknames associated with positive, negative, or neutral emotions were employed. The participants were presented these faces, verbs, and nicknames at the beginning of the experiment. When compared to neutral and negative stimuli, the study's findings showed that positive verbs and happy faces evoked enhanced positive ERPs in fronto-central regions, whereas negative posterior ERPs were evoked in temporo-parieto-occipital regions. Additionally, the study found that negative anterior ERPs were evoked in temporo-parieto-occipital regions. These results were based on the observation that joyful faces and positive sentences trigger higher positive ERPs in fronto-central regions. These findings are based on the fact that more positive ERP activity is produced in the fronto-central regions of the brain when people are shown to be smiling and using positive verbs. These results might be explained, according to the researchers, by referring to the ERPs that were studied. These findings are in line with those found in previously conducted investigations (Schupp et al., 2003; Schacht and Sommer , 2009b).

7. Responses to Facial Cues Are Faster than Responses to Speech

It was also shown that reactions to facial cues were quicker than responses to speech, with variations in latency between the two types of responses. The difference in delay between joyous feelings and positive words was around 130 milliseconds, whereas the difference for positive phrases was 380 milliseconds. It is believed that this occurs due to the fact that happy expressions have more direct access to the circuits in the brain. Even though the same brain circuits are engaged in reactions to verbal and nonverbal emotional signals, it has been shown that responses to facial stimuli are significantly quicker than responses to words. This is despite the fact that the same brain circuits are involved in both of these types of responses (Schacht & Somer, 2009a). In addition, greater responses were seen in the late positive complex (LPP), which may be interpreted as stronger late positive waves in reaction to emotionally charged verbs (both positive and negative) and furious faces. Additionally, same result was seen. These findings provide support

for the hypothesis that LPP constitutes a component of the subsequent positive wave. Schupp et al. (Kok, 2000) found that the enhanced motivational value of emotional stimuli was the reason of these results. This discovery may be credited to Schupp et al., along with a stronger attentional inclination towards visual signals. In their study on the impact of emotional content on explicit memory, Khairudin et al. (2011) made use of both photographs and facial expressions to test their hypotheses. Both the words and the images come from two distinct databases: the Emotional Norms for English Words (ANEW) database and the International Emotional Picture System (IAPS) database (IAPS). Following the conclusion of a study in which it was determined whether a specific stimulus would have a positive, a negative, or a neutral impact, that stimulus was then included into either one of two distinct studies.

According to the results, it is far simpler to recall emotional imagery than it is to do so with emotional words. In addition, the results of a recognition test revealed that an individual's capacity to recall positive emotional information was significantly higher than an individual's capacity to recall negative emotional material. This was the case because positive information was associated with a higher likelihood of being remembered. This was a conclusion that the study lent credence to. Because of the outcomes of the study, the researchers came to the conclusion that one of the primary ways in which something's emotional worth might have an effect on a person's memory is by inhibiting explicit recollection. They arrived at this conclusion as a consequence of their investigation, which led them to take the action that they did. In a second piece of study, Khairudin et al. (2012) investigated the effect that traumatic experiences have on a person's ability to recall honest information. They were able to do this by evaluating the participants' capacity to recall and distinguish facial expressions that conveyed either good feelings, negative emotions, or no emotion at all.

According to the results, a person's state of mind has a substantial influence on the quantity of information they are able to remember, and words with a positive or negative connotation are easier to recall than terms with a neutral connotation. Furthermore, the results of the identification test showed that emotional words were recalled better than those shown by the memory test. Another group explored the influence of emotions on memory by assessing the reactions of respondents to a series of video clips that produced a spectrum of emotions, including neutral,

positive, negative, and exciting content, respectively (Anderson and Shimamura , 2005). (Anderson and Shimamura , 2005).

The results of an experiment that tested people's ability to remember words and recognize their context indicated that people had a worse memory for phrases connected with emotionally upsetting movie clips than they did for terms associated with emotionally neutral, positive, and stimulating movies. The findings of the experiment demonstrated that one should expect this to be the case. Additionally, research has revealed a connection between viewing emotionally engaging movie clips and improved context recognition memory, but not when it comes to free word recall. This correlation was found between the two phenomena. On the other hand, when it comes to free recall of the words in issue, this association is not there at all. As a result, there is a need for more study to understand whether emotional signals improve recognition memory or recall memory.

People appear to remember emotional information better for recognition rather than recall; Consequently, this leads to suggest that emotional stimuli boost recognition memory. In a nutshell, the amygdala reacts to emotional cues (both words and images) when there is a larger allocation of attentional resources to emotional visuals, which is also accompanied by big late positive waves of LPP in the posterior area. a tip that, when followed, leads to better memory. In addition, when there is a stronger allocation of attentional resources to emotional images, big late positive waves of LPP in the posterior area are present at the same time. In addition, the response to standardized stimuli and the types of stimuli that were discussed in the previous section that you need to be aware of arises when there is a greater allocation of attentional resources to emotional pictures which is accompanied by large late positive waves of LPP in the anterior region. This is something that you need to be aware of. medial The prefrontal cortex (mPFC) and left superior frontal gyrus demonstrated a substantial increase in oxy-HB when shown negative photographs , compared to their activity when shown neutral photos.

The data provide credence to this line of reasoning. It is abundantly evident that more study is required in this particular field as a consequence of the fact that the participants' hemodynamic state did not alter noticeably either when they saw the visual representation or when they carried out the n-back task. These procedures are used to examine how the brain stores memories of one's emotions. This section gives an overview of six crucial factors to consider while preparing an experiment and deciding the proper technique to follow. These problems need to be taken into

account while putting up an experiment and creating the suitable technique . Before going on to the following part, it is important to take these into consideration.

8. Individual-Level Variations

Numerous studies have demonstrated that there are additional elements at play in the way that individuals absorb their emotions, in addition to the vast range of individual variances in the way that people do so. Alterations to the Social Environment's Highest Level Some examples of these include an individual's intellectual ability (Brackett et al., 2004), personality qualities (Montag and Panksepp, 2017), and sexual orientation (Brackett et al., 2004). (Montag and Panksepp , 2017). (Cahill, 2003). [Cahill] Additionally, sex hormones and personality qualities (such as extraversion and neuroticism) seem to have an influence on an individual's capacity to govern emotional processing as well as their reactions to emotional stimuli. This is the case regardless of whether the individual is male or female. Despite the fact that sex hormones do not directly influence emotional reactions, this is nevertheless the case. This occurs regardless of whether the individual in issue is male or female. It is feasible to lower the incidence of false positive findings that are brought on by individual differences by doing proper screening utilizing psychological testing and maintaining gender equality in experimental cohorts. This would bring about the desired effect. This will result in a portrayal of the population that is more true to the whole.

9. Conclusion

In addition, research has shown that older persons have a greater amount of experience with psychological stress and emotional experiences. Because of this familiarity, older persons are more likely to have optimism biases in their emotional processing, and they have more control over their emotions than younger ones. This is due to the fact that people of a more advanced age have lived through a greater range of the highs and lows that life has to offer (Urry and Gross , 2010; Allard and Kensinger , 2014). When doing research on mental or emotional processes, taking into account the ages of the people who will be participating in the sample group is an absolutely necessary step. It makes no difference whether the studies look at adults or children; this is always the case. This is due to the fact that the mental and emotional processes that make up a person present

themselves in a wide range of distinct ways. In the context of experimental research, the choice of emotional stimuli to use may often be broken down into two categories:

- *disjointed emotional and*
- *Dimensional emotions including valence, arousal, dominance, and familiarity.*

Depending on the sort of study that is being carried out, one may classify emotional triggers as either discrete or dimensional. [Citation needed] The first group discusses the range of feelings that an individual is capable of experiencing by themselves, while the second group discusses the range of feelings that may be rated on a scale (Russell, 1980; Barrett, 1998). The second one has images obtained from a database known as IAPS and text obtained from another database known as ANEW. Both of these databases are freely available to the general public and anyone doing research that is not for commercial use. In order to guarantee that the experimental tasks are suitable for the investigation of emotional processing in learning and memory, it is necessary to take into consideration a number of crucial aspects, including the proper selection of emotional stimuli. This is due to the fact that there are a wide variety of distinct kinds of emotional stimuli. It is feasible to accomplish this objective if careful consideration is given to the choice of the appropriate emotional stimuli.

10. References

Arnold MB (1960) Emotion and personality.
New York: Columbia University
Press.

"Aron AR, Robbins TW, Poldrack RA (2004)
Inhibition and the right inferior
frontal cortex." ("Cognition and
emotion - Scholarpedia") Trends
Cogn Sci 8:170-177.

"Barbas H (1995) Anatomic basis of
cognitive-emotional interactions in
the primate prefrontal cortex."
("Neural Systems Laboratory -
Publications - Boston University")
Neuroscience and Biobehavioral
Reviews 19:449-510.

Bargh JA (1997) The automaticity of
everyday life. In: Advances in social

- cognition (Wyer Jr. RS, ed), pp 1-61. ("Cognition and emotion - Scholarpedia") Mahwah, NJ: Erlbaum.
- "Bishop SJ (2007) Neurocognitive mechanisms of anxiety: an integrative account." ("Cognition and emotion - Scholarpedia") Trends Cogn Sci 11:307-316.
- "Bishop SJ, Duncan J, Lawrence AD (2004) State anxiety modulation of the amygdala response to unattended threat-related stimuli." ("Foraging under Competition: The Neural Basis of Input-Matching in ...") J Neurosci 24:10364-10368.
- Bishop SJ, Jenkins R, Lawrence AD (2007) Neural processing of fearful faces: effects of anxiety are gated by perceptual capacity limitations. Cereb Cortex 17:1595-1603.
- Bornstein R. (1989). Exposure and affect: Overview and meta-analysis of research, 1968-1987. Psychological Bulletin 106: 265-289.
- Bradley MM, Greenwald MK, Petry MC, Lang PJ (1992) Remembering pictures: pleasure and arousal in memory. J Exp Psychol Learn Mem Cogn 18:379-390.
- Cahill L, Haier RJ, Fallon J, Alkire MT, Tang C, Keator D, Wu J, McGaugh JL (1996) Amygdala activity at encoding correlated with long-term, free recall of emotional information. Proc Natl Acad Sci USA 93:8016-8021.
- "Damasio AR (1994) Descartes' error: Emotion, reason, and the human brain." ("Descartes Error Emotion Reason And The Human Brain") New York: GP Putnam.
- Damasio AR (1999) The feeling of what happens: body and emotion in the making of consciousness. ("The feeling of what happens : body and emotion in the making of ...") New York: Harcourt Brace.
- Dolan R (2003) Emotion, cognition, and behavior. Science 298:1191-1194.
- Duncan S, Barrett LF (2007) Affect is a form of cognition: A neurobiological analysis. Cognition and Emotion 21:1184-1211.
- "Gray JR, Braver TS, Raichle ME (2002) Integration of emotion and cognition in the lateral prefrontal cortex." ("Brain Systems Mediating Cognitive

Interference by Emotional Distraction ...") Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences USA 99:4115-4120.

Haidt J (2003) The moral emotions. In: Handbook of Affective Sciences (Davidson RJ, Scherer KR, Goldsmith HH, eds), pp 852-870. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

"Heimer L, Van Hoesen GW (2006) The limbic lobe and its output channels: implications for emotional functions

and adaptive behavior." ("Cognition and emotion - Scholarpedia") Neurosci Biobehav Rev 30:126-147.

"Hilgetag CC, Burns GA, O'Neill MA, Scannell JW, Young MP (2000) Anatomical connectivity defines the organization of clusters of cortical areas in the macaque monkey and the cat." ("Hierarchical Organization of Human Cortical Networks in Health and ...") Philos Trans R Soc Lond B Biol Sci 355:91-110.